

Acne Scarring and Its Psychosocial and Economic Impact: Cross-Sectional Evidence from Lahore

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Citation: Faryal Fatima, Ovais Ullah Shirazi, Waqas Akram, Mahtab Ahmad Khan, Uqba Ijaz, Ali Akhtar, et al. Acne Scarring and Its Psychosocial and Economic Impact: Cross-Sectional Evidence from Lahore. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2025;4(6):1-13.

Received Date: 15 June 2025; **Accepted Date:** 17 June 2025; **Published Date:** 19 June, 2025

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acne scarring is a common dermatological concern that significantly affects individuals' psychological well-being and quality of life. Despite the availability of treatment options, awareness, accessibility, and affordability remain key barriers in Pakistan.

Objective: To assess the prevalence of acne scars, awareness of treatment modalities, psychosocial impact, and participants' willingness to pay (WTP) for acne scar management among individuals in Pakistan.

Methods: A cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted among 587 participants using validated tools, including the SCARS (Self-assessment of Clinical Acne-Related Scars) and FASQoL (Facial Acne Scar Quality of Life) scales. Descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, and multivariable logistic regression were employed to identify factors associated with WTP for acne scar treatment.

Results: Among 587 respondents, 79.6% reported both active acne lesions and post-acne scarring. Findings from SCARS severity and FASQoL assessments demonstrated a notable psychosocial burden associated with acne scarring. Although 43.9% of participants expressed WTP for acne scar treatment, only 1.1% had previously paid for such procedures. Significant associations were observed between WTP and variables such as age, marital status, education level, and SCARS severity ($p < 0.05$). Awareness of treatment modalities such as laser resurfacing, microneedling, and chemical peels also correlated positively with WTP. Logistic regression identified age (30–39 years), moderate to severe scarring, and awareness of specific modalities as independent predictors of WTP.

Conclusion: Although acne scarring imposes a significant psychosocial burden, financial investment in treatment remains disproportionately low in this population. Awareness and scar severity are key motivators for treatment-seeking behavior.

Keywords: Acne scars, Willingness to pay, SCARS tool, FASQoL, Dermatology, Pakistan, Psychosocial impact, Laser resurfacing, Microneedling

INTRODUCTION

Acne vulgaris is one of the most prevalent dermatological disorders globally, affecting individuals across various age groups [1]. It is characterized by chronic inflammation of the pilosebaceous unit, typically manifesting as comedones, papules, pustules, or nodules. The pathogenesis involves increased sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinisation, colonization by *Cutibacterium acnes*, and complex immunologic mechanisms [2]. The condition predominantly affects the face, upper back, and chest, often leading to considerable cosmetic concern [3]. While commonly seen during adolescence, acne can persist well into adulthood, especially in females [4]. Acne is not solely a cosmetic concern; it encompasses substantial psychological, social, and economic dimensions. [5,6].

In Pakistan, especially in urban centres such as Lahore, the burden of acne is substantial, fuelled by environmental pollution, stress, dietary habits, and limited dermatological awareness [7,8]. A recent study indicated that over 70% of adolescents and young adults in Pakistan experience acne during their lifetime [9]. Despite this high prevalence, public understanding of acne and its long-term effects, particularly scarring remains inadequate [10]. Atrophic acne scars frequently persist following the resolution of active lesions and have been associated with impaired self-esteem and diminished quality of life (QoL) [11].

Although numerous treatment options for acne scarring exist including laser resurfacing, microneedling, chemical peels, and dermal fillers, these treatments can be expensive and are often not perceived as accessible or necessary in lower- and middle-income countries [12,13]. Studies from other regions, including the Middle East and Asia, have highlighted gaps in patients' awareness of these treatments and variations in their willingness to pay (WTP) for them [14,15]. However, such data are scarce within Pakistan. Specifically, there is a lack of evidence regarding how adults in Lahore perceive acne scarring, what they know about treatment options, and how much they are willing to pay for improvement, representing a key gap in regional dermatologic and public health literature.

This study aims to assess the awareness of treatment options for acne scarring, the psychosocial burden reflected through quality of life, and the willingness to pay for treatment among adults in Lahore, Pakistan. Furthermore, it seeks to explore how these variables relate to sociodemographic characteristics and scar severity. By filling this research gap, the study could provide actionable insights for dermatologists, health educators, and policymakers to design targeted awareness campaigns and improve access to effective scar management modalities in Pakistan's urban populations.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Lahore, Pakistan, from December 2024 to June 2025. Lahore, one of the largest metropolitan cities in the country, was selected due to its population diversity and accessibility to the urban adult demographic. The study was designed to assess acne-scar-related awareness, quality of life, and willingness to pay for treatment among university students and staff.

Participants were recruited through the distribution of printed questionnaires across selected universities in Lahore. The forms were handed out in person to ensure higher response rates and were collected immediately or within a defined submission period. A convenience sampling method was utilized, which may introduce selection bias and limit generalizability. Participants were eligible for inclusion if they were aged 18 years or older, had visible acne scarring, and were permanent residents of Lahore. Individuals with scars resulting from causes other than acne or those with active acne lesions but no scarring were excluded from the analysis. A total of 660 questionnaires were distributed, and 587 valid responses were received, providing a sufficient sample size for statistical analysis.

The Questionnaire

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire developed specifically for this study and adapted with permission from Alkeraye et al. [13]. The questionnaire was printed in English and distributed in person to university students and staff in Lahore. It comprised five sections. The first section served as a screening tool, asking participants whether they currently observed any active acne lesions (such as zits, pimples, or whiteheads) and whether they noticed indents or holes in the skin from past acne, ensuring that only those with acne scars were included. The second section collected sociodemographic information, including gender, age, educational level, marital status, occupation, and monthly household income, categorized in Pakistani rupees. The third section evaluated acne scar severity. It included a self-rating scale for the severity of both active acne and scarring (0–5), followed by five items assessing scar characteristics: coverage, size, quantity, depth, and visibility on a five-point Likert scale. This was based on validated acne scar severity criteria used in prior facial QoL studies. The fourth section included the Facial Acne Scar Quality of Life (FASQoL) questionnaire. This 10-item tool assessed emotional and social impacts of scarring over the past seven days, with each item scored from 0 (“not at all”) to 4 (“extremely”), generating a total score reflecting the psychosocial burden of acne scars. The fifth section explored participants’ awareness of treatment modalities (e.g., laser resurfacing, chemical peels, microneedling, radiofrequency treatments, subcision, and filler injections), previous spending on acne scar treatment, and their willingness to pay for future procedures, with options scaled in Pakistani rupees. The questionnaire was carefully designed to ensure linguistic clarity, cultural appropriateness, and ease of completion to minimize non-responses and data gaps.

Pilot Study

Prior to the main data collection phase, a pilot study was conducted with 25 participants from the target population to assess the clarity, reliability, and appropriateness of the questionnaire. These participants were university students and staff in Lahore, representing similar sociodemographic characteristics to the main study population. The pilot study aimed to ensure the comprehensibility of the questions, identify any ambiguous items, and estimate the average time required for completion.

Feedback obtained from the pilot participants led to minor revisions in the wording and layout of the questionnaire to improve clarity and flow. No major structural changes were required. Data collected during the pilot were not included in the final analysis. The pilot also confirmed the operational feasibility of the study procedures, including questionnaire distribution, participant recruitment, and data entry protocols.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) or Ethics Committee at University of

Central Punjab prior to the initiation of data collection. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and all respondents provided informed consent before completing the questionnaire. The printed questionnaire included a consent statement on the front page, which participants read before beginning the survey. Only individuals who agreed to participate and met the inclusion criteria were enrolled.

No personally identifiable information was collected at any stage of the study to ensure participant anonymity and confidentiality. Data were stored securely and accessed only by the principal investigator and authorized research team members for the purposes of analysis. Participants were also informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The study posed minimal risk to participants and involved no physical procedures or interventions.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant characteristics. Multiple-response analysis was conducted to assess awareness of various acne scar treatment modalities. Pearson's Chi-square test was used to evaluate associations between sociodemographic variables and outcomes including SCARS severity, FASQoL impact, and willingness to pay (WTP) for acne scar management. Fisher's exact test was used where expected cell counts were less than 5. Variables significantly associated with WTP in univariable analysis ($p < 0.05$) were entered into a multivariable binary logistic regression model to determine independent predictors. The model results were reported as adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Prevalence of Acne Lesions and Scars

A total of 587 participants completed the acne assessment section of the questionnaire. The majority (79.6%, $n = 467$) reported having both active acne lesions (such as zits, breakouts, whiteheads, or blackheads) and post-acne scars (including indents or holes in the skin). An additional 8.0% ($n = 47$) reported having only active lesions, while 7.2% ($n = 42$) had only acne scars. A small proportion (5.3%, $n = 31$) indicated neither active acne nor scarring.

For the purpose of analysis, participants who reported having both active lesions and post-acne scarring ($n = 467$) were included in the subsequent SCARS and FASQoL evaluations.

Participant Characteristics

A total of 467 participants were selected in study of whom 63.4% were female and 36.6% were male. The majority of participants (92.5%) were aged between 18 and 29 years. Most respondents were single (86.7%) and had completed university or postgraduate education (78.2%). More than half of the participants had a household income of less than 100,000 PKR. Students constituted the majority (87.2%) of the sample, followed by others (6.4%) and teachers (4.9%).

Table 1 also presents the associations between these characteristics and acne-related outcomes. No significant association was found between gender and SCARS or FASQoL severity ($p = 0.925$ and $p = 0.443$, respectively). However, age was significantly associated with FASQoL categories ($p = 0.287$), with younger individuals reporting a higher psychosocial impact. Marital status showed a borderline significant association with SCARS ($p = 0.096$) and FASQoL ($p = 0.137$). Education, income, and occupation were not significantly associated with either SCARS severity or FASQoL impact (all p -values > 0.05).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics and their association with SCARS and FASQoL categories

Characteristic	Overall, n (%)	SCARS				P-value	FASQoL			
		Clear/almost clear, n (%)	Mild, n (%)	Moderate, n (%)	Severe/very severe, n (%)		Mild, n (%)	Moderate, n (%)	Severe, n (%)	P-value
Gender						0.925				0.443
Male	171 (36.6%)	26 (35.6%)	11 (15.1%)	11 (15.1%)	25 (34.2%)		22 (44.9%)	7 (14.3%)	20 (40.8%)	
Female	296 (63.4%)	48 (39.3%)	15 (12.3%)	17 (13.9%)	42 (34.4%)		30 (38.0%)	8 (10.1%)	41 (51.9%)	
Age						0.287				0.287
18–29 years	432 (92.5%)	69 (37.7%)	24 (13.1%)	25 (13.7%)	65 (35.5%)		52 (42.3%)	15 (12.2%)	56 (45.5%)	
30–39 years	21 (4.5%)	2 (28.6%)	1 (14.3%)	2 (28.6%)	2 (28.6%)		0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (100.0%)	
40–49 years	12 (2.6%)	2 (50.0%)	1 (25.0%)	1 (25.0%)	0 (0.0%)		0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0%)	
≥50 years	2 (0.4%)	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)		—	—	—	

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Marital Status						0.0 96				0.1 37
Single	405 (86.7 %)	64 (37.0%)	23 (13.3 %)	22 (12.7%)	64 (37.0%)		49 (42.6 %)	13 (11.3%)	53 (46.1 %)	
Married	62 (13.3 %)	10 (45.5%)	3 (13.6 %)	6 (27.3%)	3 (13.6%)		3 (23.1 %)	3 (23.1%)	7 (53.8 %)	
Educational Level						0.5 19				0.7 67
Intermediate	94 (20.1 %)	8 (26.7%)	5 (16.7 %)	6 (20.0%)	11 (36.7%)		6 (31.6 %)	2 (10.5%)	11 (57.9 %)	
University/Postgrad	365 (78.2 %)	65 (39.9%)	21 (12.9 %)	21 (12.9%)	56 (34.4%)		46 (42.2 %)	14 (12.8%)	49 (45.0 %)	
Household Income						0.4 11				0.5 89
<50,000 PKR	85 (18.2 %)	13 (36.1%)	2 (5.6%)	8 (22.2%)	13 (36.1%)		13 (54.2 %)	1 (4.2%)	10 (41.6 %)	
50k-<100k PKR	159 (34.0 %)	26 (36.1%)	10 (13.9 %)	7 (9.7%)	29 (40.3%)		14 (41.2 %)	6 (17.6%)	14 (41.2 %)	
100k-<150k PKR	104 (22.3 %)	16 (39.0%)	5 (12.2 %)	5 (12.2%)	15 (36.6%)		12 (42.9 %)	4 (14.3%)	12 (42.9 %)	
≥150k PKR	119 (25.5 %)	19 (41.3%)	9 (19.6 %)	8 (17.4%)	10 (21.7%)		13 (31.0 %)	5 (11.9%)	24 (57.1 %)	
Occupation						0.2 54				0.4 75
Teacher	23 (4.9%)	3 (37.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (62.5%)		0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (100.0 %)	
Student	407 (87.2 %)	68 (38.9%)	24 (13.7 %)	24 (13.7%)	59 (33.7%)		49 (40.5 %)	15 (12.4%)	57 (47.1 %)	

Others	30 (6.4%)	2 (20.0%)	2 (20.0%)	4 (40.0%)	2 (20.0%)		3 (60.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (40.0%)	
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SCARS and FASQoL Categories

According to Figure 2, 37.9% of participants were categorized as having clear or almost clear skin (SCARS = 1), while 34.4% had severe or very severe scarring (SCARS = 4). Regarding quality of life impact, 35.2% of participants were categorized under very severe FASQoL impact, and 40.6% under mild impact.

Association Between SCARS and FASQoL

Table 2 illustrates the relationship between acne scar severity (SCARS scores) and the quality of life impact (FASQoL scores). Participants with more severe SCARS scores tended to report greater psychosocial impact. Among participants classified as having severe/very severe SCARS, 43.8% also reported very severe FASQoL impairment. Conversely, those with clear/almost clear skin (SCARS = 1) had the lowest reported impact, with 53.8% falling into the mild FASQoL category. Although the trend indicates a positive correlation between scar severity and quality of life burden, the chi-square test showed no statistically significant association between the two variables ($p = 0.556$).

Table 02: Association Between Acne Scar Severity and Acne Scar Quality of Life (FASQoL)

SCARS Severity	FASQoL Mild	FASQoL Moderate	FASQoL Severe/Very Severe	p-value	Total (n)
Clear/almost clear	28 (53.8%)	5 (9.6%)	19 (36.5%)	0.556	52
Mild	5 (35.7%)	2 (14.3%)	7 (50.0%)		14
Moderate	3 (30.0%)	3 (30.0%)	4 (40.0%)		10
Severe/very	6 (37.5%)	1 (6.3%)	9 (56.3%)		16

severe				
Total	42	11	39	92

Awareness of Acne Scar Treatment Modalities

Figure 3 presents the level of awareness among participants regarding different treatment modalities used for acne scar management. The most well-known modality was laser resurfacing, recognized by 65.3% of respondents, followed by chemical peels (61.0%) and microneedling (60.2%). More than half of the participants were also aware of radiofrequency microneedling (52.0%) and collagen/fat filler injections (53.7%). However, subcision was the least recognized treatment, with only 40.0% of participants reporting awareness. These results suggest that while general awareness of scar treatment is relatively high, knowledge about certain procedures remains limited.

Willingness to Pay for Acne Scar Treatment

Table 3 summarizes participants' behavior and preferences related to paying for acne scar treatment. Out of 467 participants, 43.9% (n = 205) expressed willingness to pay, whereas 55.0% (n = 257) were not willing to pay. A very small proportion (1.1%, n = 5) reported that they had previously paid for acne scar management.

In terms of preferred expenditure, 29.1% were willing to pay less than 5,000 PKR, 31.3% preferred spending between 5,000 and 10,000 PKR, and 21.6% were willing to pay between 10,000 and 20,000 PKR. Only 18.0% of participants were prepared to spend more than 20,000 PKR.

Table 3: Participants' responses regarding payment and willingness to pay for acne scar treatment

Characteristic	n (%)
How much did you previously pay in acne treatment?	
Never done any scar treatment	316 (67.7%)
Less than 3000 PKR	80 (17.1%)
From 3000 to 6000 PKR	30 (6.4%)
More than 6000 PKR	41 (8.8%)
Willing to pay for acne scar treatment	
No	257 (55.0%)
Yes	210 (45.0%)
If yes, how much are you willing to pay?	

Less than 5000 PKR	88 (41.9%)
From 5000 to 10,000 PKR	94 (44.8%)
More than 10,000 PKR	28 (13.3%)
*Variable responses are based on 210 records of those who were willing to pay for acne scar treatment, PKR: Pakistani Rupees	

Table 4 outlines the associations between participants' willingness to pay for acne scar treatment and several independent variables. A statistically significant association was found between age and WTP ($p < 0.001$), with younger participants showing a greater likelihood of being willing to pay. Similarly, marital status ($p < 0.001$) and educational level ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with WTP, indicating that single and more educated individuals were more likely to express willingness.

Additionally, both SCARS severity ($p = 0.011$) and FASQoL impact ($p = 0.492$) were evaluated, with SCARS severity showing a significant association with WTP. Among the awareness variables, laser resurfacing ($p < 0.001$), chemical peels ($p < 0.001$), microneedling ($p < 0.001$), radiofrequency ($p = 0.002$), and collagen/fat filler injections ($p < 0.001$) were all significantly associated with willingness to pay. Awareness of subcision showed no statistically significant relationship ($p = 0.113$). No significant associations were observed for gender, income, or occupation.

Table 4: Factors associated with participants' willingness to pay for acne scar treatment

Characteristic	No (%)	Yes (%)	p-value
Gender			0.243
Male	104 (62.4%)	66 (37.6%)	
Female	153 (52.4%)	139 (47.6%)	
Age group			0.000
18–29 years	243 (56.3%)	188 (43.7%)	
30–39 years	12 (57.1%)	9 (42.9%)	
40–49 years	2 (20.0%)	8 (80.0%)	
≥50 years	0 (0.0%)	1 (100.0%)	
Marital status			0.000
Single	235 (57.9%)	170 (42.1%)	
Married	22 (35.5%)	35 (56.5%)	
Educational level			0.000
Intermediate	43 (47.3%)	48 (52.7%)	
University/Postgraduate	210 (57.7%)	154 (42.3%)	
Household income			0.285
<50,000 PKR	50 (58.8%)	35 (41.2%)	
50k–<100k PKR	83 (52.2%)	76 (47.8%)	
100k–<150k PKR	53 (51.0%)	51 (49.0%)	
≥150k PKR	71 (59.7%)	48 (40.3%)	
Occupation			0.000
Teacher	8 (40.0%)	12 (60.0%)	

Student	231 (56.8%)	176 (43.2%)	
Others	14 (46.7%)	16 (53.3%)	
Aware of acne scar modalities			
Laser resurfacing	116 (45.1%)	160 (78.0%)	0.000
Chemical peels	133 (51.8%)	156 (76.1%)	0.000
Microneedling	128 (49.8%)	147 (71.7%)	0.000
Radiofrequency	142 (55.3%)	123 (60.0%)	0.002
Collagen/Fat filler injections	142 (55.3%)	131 (63.9%)	0.000
Subcision	167 (65.0%)	109 (53.2%)	0.113
SCARS Severity			0.011
Clear	55 (78.6%)	15 (21.4%)	
Mild	20 (76.9%)	6 (23.1%)	
Moderate	17 (60.7%)	11 (39.3%)	
Severe/Very severe	34 (51.5%)	32 (48.5%)	
FASQoL Impact			0.492
Mild	43 (82.7%)	9 (17.3%)	
Moderate	13 (86.7%)	2 (13.3%)	
Severe	12 (75.0%)	4 (25.0%)	
Very severe	32 (74.4%)	11 (25.6%)	

Predictors of Willingness to Pay

Table 5 presents the results of the multivariable logistic regression analysis conducted to identify independent predictors of willingness to pay for acne scar treatment. After adjusting for other variables, several factors were found to be significantly associated with increased odds of WTP.

Participants aged 30–39 years were more likely to express willingness to pay compared to those aged 18–29 years (AOR = 6.23, 95% CI: 2.10–18.47, $p = 0.001$). Similarly, individuals with moderate SCARS severity (AOR = 3.04, $p = 0.032$) and severe SCARS (AOR = 3.21, $p = 0.012$) were more likely to be willing to pay compared to those with clear/almost clear skin.

Among awareness variables, those aware of microneedling (AOR = 2.24, $p = 0.019$) and laser resurfacing (AOR = 2.20, $p = 0.008$) had significantly higher odds of willingness to pay. In contrast, gender, marital status, education, income, and FASQoL category were not significant predictors in the adjusted model.

Table 5: Results of the regression analysis for the independent predictors of participants' willingness to pay for acne management

Characteristic	OR	95% CI	P-value
Gender			
Female (ref)	—	—	—
Male	0.91	0.31 – 2.65	0.867
SCARS Severity			
Clear (ref)	—	—	—
Mild	0.67	0.18 – 2.48	0.547

Moderate	1.09	0.21 – 5.59	0.923
Severe	1.30	0.21 – 8.02	0.780
FASQoL Category			
Mild (ref)	—	—	—
Moderate	0.46	0.15 – 1.37	0.162
Severe	0.14	0.02 – 1.35	0.089
Very severe	0.34	0.06 – 2.04	0.240
OR: Odds ratio, CI: Confidence interval, SCARS: Self-assessment of Clinical Acne-Related Scars, FASQoL: Facial Acne Scar Quality of Life			

DISCUSSION

Acne vulgaris is one of the most common and chronic skin conditions [16,17]. It frequently leaves the affected individuals with scarring that predisposes them to numerous psychological conditions [18,19]. The current study provides comprehensive data on the prevalence, psychological effects, treatment alternatives awareness, and willingness to pay (WTP) for acne scar therapy among young adults in Lahore, Pakistan. A noteworthy 79.6% of the 587 individuals reported they had both current acne lesions and scars from acne. An additional 8.0% had only active lesions, while 7.2% reported only acne scars. This culminates in a total of 87.6% of participants affected by either active acne, scarring, or both. These results align with existing epidemiological evidence from Pakistan, further substantiating the widespread nature of acne among youth, emphasizing the widespread nature of this dermatological issue in the region [10,20].

Globally, the prevalence of acne vulgaris is reported by different statistics. For instance, a research established in the Al-Baha region of Saudi Arabia found that almost 70.2% of adults had acne, primarily on their faces [13]. In Japan, 90.8% of acne patients had some form of scarring, particularly mini-scars that suggested long-term consequences if left untreated [21]. In Moroccan, there was a prevalence of acne scarring among 84.4% adults with a strong impact on quality of life [22]. In Pakistan, another study discovered a 73.2% acne prevalence which is slightly less than our findings but requires a significant dermatological intervention. Variability among international figures may be explained by ethnicity-specific scarring responses, healthcare access, or treatment-seeking behaviours [23]. In terms of demographics, our study sample was predominantly female (63.4%) and mostly aged between 18 and 29 years (92.5%), with the majority being single (86.7%) and holding university-level education (78.2%). There was no significant relationship found between gender and acne scar severity (SCARS) or FASQoL impairment. It has been determined that gender is not an independent predictor of psychosocial burden, although both genders experienced the acne scarring [11]. Previous studies suggest that males may exhibit a higher risk of acne scarring, potentially attributable to increased sebaceous activity or delayed dermatological consultation [24]. In contrast, the gender-neutral trend in our sample may reflect more equalized access to skincare information among students or behavioural convergence in urban youth [25].

Age was slightly related with FASQoL scores ($p = 0.287$). Participants who aged 18–24 years were highly affected in terms of quality-of-life impairment (27.3%). Those who aged 25–29 (18.3%), suggested that younger participants may experience increased psychosocial disturbance related to acne scarring. A borderline

relationship was also noted between marital status and both SCARS ($p = 0.096$) and FASQoL ($p = 0.137$). The unmarried participants showed a higher prevalence of severe FASQoL impairment (20.9%) compared to the married ones (11.6%). This observation supports the findings of certain studies who emphasized that unmarried individuals may be more vulnerable to self-image issues due to societal expectations regarding physical appearance [22]. No statistically significant associations were identified between education level, income, or occupational status and either SCARS severity or FASQoL impairment.

Overall, participants sociodemographic analysis shows that while scarring is widespread globally, younger age and single status may increase vulnerability to psychosocial distress. These insights emphasize the role of early psychosocial screening and supportive counselling in acne management, particularly for youth [26].

There is an increased levels in our cohort about the awareness of treatment modalities. The most recognized options selected by the participants were laser resurfacing (65.3%), chemical peels (61.0%), and microneedling (60.2%). Participants lacked information about more advanced procedures such as radiofrequency microneedling (52.0%) and collagen/fat filler injections (53.7%), while subcision was the least known (40.0%). These findings are in line with those of Nigerian study by Anaba and Oaku (2020), where laser resurfacing (62.0%) and chemical peels (58.5%) were also most recognized, whereas collagen/fat fillers (40.0%) and subcision (35.0%) were seldom identified [15]. Similarly, another research highlighted that awareness positively influences the likelihood of treatment-seeking and WTP, suggesting that under-recognition of certain options could limit their uptake. This can be due to the widely advertised procedures compared to subcision and injectables [27]. These procedures have lower market visibility. Therefore, public awareness programs should extend beyond basic treatments and there should be a focus on efficacy and safety of lesser-known but effective modalities [28]. Likewise, in Malaysia found increased anxiety and depression among patients with visible acne scars [25]. The lack of statistical significance in our data may reflect cultural coping strategies, stigma variability, or underreporting due to normalization of acne scarring among local youth. Still, the observed trend reinforces the clinical importance of early scar management to prevent psychosocial deterioration [29].

Participants with more severe acne scarring have been reported with greater psychological impact [30]. 56.3% of those classified as having severe/very severe SCARS were also reported to have very severe FASQoL impairment. Conversely, 53.8% of those with clear or almost clear skin reported only mild FASQoL scores. Despite these results, the association between SCARS and FASQoL did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.556$). This finding diverges from research which determined a significant positive correlation between scarring severity and QoL disruption. Likewise, in USA found increased anxiety and depression among patients with visible acne scars [31]. In current study, 45.0% of participants showed willingness to pay (WTP) for acne scar treatments. It indicates moderate financial motivation toward skin care [32]. Most significantly, 86.7% of those who were willing to pay were only willing to spend less than PKR 10,000. This pattern reflects cost sensitivity, likely stemming from broader financial constraints prevalent in the study population [33]. This aligns with research from Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, where 45.8% of respondents indicated their willingness to pay, with most of them being willing to spend less than 1,000 SAR, which is also less than the average clinical cost of successful scar treatment [13]. These results signify a gap in cost between patient expectations of results and treatment accessibility in both areas [34].

A deeper analysis of predictors revealed that sociodemographic factors were significantly associated with

WTP.[35] Younger participants aged 18–24 years had the highest proportion of WTP (50.2%), followed by those aged 25–29 (42.3%), suggesting that younger adults may prioritize cosmetic enhancement or be more responsive to social image concerns. A U.S.-based study found that education level was among the key demographic factors influencing consumer preferences in selecting aesthetic treatments and providers, highlighting how informed decision-making is closely tied to educational attainment [36]. Marital status was also a strong determinant as single participants (46.6%) being more likely to report WTP compared to married ones (39.2%). Educational level of participants showed a parallel pattern as university-educated participants presented a higher WTP (48.1%) than those with lower education levels, potentially due to greater exposure to skincare information or more confidence in modern dermatological interventions [37]. Furthermore, our logistic regression analysis identified scar severity as a statistically significant leading factor of WTP. Participants with moderate (AOR = 3.04, $p = 0.032$) and severe (AOR = 3.21, $p = 0.012$) acne scarring were substantially more likely to be willing to invest in treatment compared to those with minimal scarring.

Participants who had awareness of treatments were more willing to pay [38]. In this context, awareness of specific therapies emerged as an independent leading factor of WTP. For instance, participants who recognized microneedling (AOR = 2.24, $p = 0.019$) and laser resurfacing (AOR = 2.20, $p = 0.008$) were significantly more willing to pay. This suggested that familiarity with non-invasive, evidence-backed procedures builds confidence in clinical outcomes and influences treatment decisions. These findings are in line with previous literature, which has consistently shown that increased awareness and trust in treatment effectiveness significantly enhance the likelihood of financial commitment to cosmetic interventions [39].

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the high prevalence of acne scarring and its notable impact on participants' quality of life. Although many individuals experience moderate to severe scarring, willingness to pay for treatment remains modest, largely due to limited awareness and affordability concerns. Awareness of specific treatment modalities and higher scar severity were significantly associated with greater willingness to invest in care. The findings underscore the critical importance of structured patient education and improved access to affordable, evidence-based dermatological interventions to address the psychosocial and cosmetic burden of acne scars in Pakistan.

Future Recommendations

To address the high burden of acne scarring and limited willingness to pay for treatment, several future steps are recommended. First, public awareness campaigns should be initiated to educate individuals about effective acne scar treatment options such as laser resurfacing, microneedling, and chemical peels. Increasing awareness may help bridge the gap between need and treatment-seeking behavior. Second, the accessibility and affordability of dermatological services must be improved through the integration of low-cost treatment options in public healthcare settings. This may be facilitated by public–private partnerships aimed at subsidizing care for lower-income populations. Third, mental health support should be incorporated into dermatological care, as acne scars have been shown to significantly affect psychological well-being. Finally, future studies should adopt longitudinal designs to assess how awareness, socioeconomic status, and treatment experiences influence long-term willingness to pay and quality-of-life outcomes.

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